

SOCIAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF COVERAGE THROUGH GEOGRAPHIC ACCESSIBILITY OF EDUCATIONAL FACILITIES IN A SMALL COLOMBIAN MUNICIPALITY: CASE STUDY, PITALITO

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Abstract

Education, as a fundamental pillar, plays an essential role in the development and strengthening of a society, driving not only economic growth but also fostering cohesion among various ethnic groups. For this reason, it is of utmost importance to conduct a thorough analysis of the current conditions of access to educational institutions, specifically in the case of Pitalito - Huila, to determine the level of accessibility and coverage provided by the local educational system. This analysis aims to ensure that travel costs are minimized while maximizing the effectiveness and efficiency of the educational institutions. The methodology utilized in this research is centered around territorial accessibility, incorporating geo-statistical models supported by advanced digital tools. These tools allow for precise interpretation and easy replication of the results, ensuring that the findings are both accurate and applicable to similar contexts. This comprehensive approach not only addresses the immediate needs of the educational system but also contributes to a deeper understanding of how education can be more effectively integrated into the broader social and economic fabric of the region.

Keywords: Accessibility, education, geostatistics, coverage, development.

INTRODUCTION

Education, as a driving force of development, plays a pivotal role in shaping and strengthening a city. It is regarded as a fundamental and high-quality service that must incorporate effective accessibility features to meet the growing demands of the community. Therefore, ensuring adequate educational coverage is crucial not only for supporting population growth but also for stimulating socio-economic progress. Achieving this requires careful evaluation and assurance of access to educational institutions through infrastructure improvements managed by local authorities.

In our case study, the assessment of accessibility to educational centers is focused on the municipality of Pitalito, located in the Huila department, in the southwestern region of Colombia. This municipality lies in

the Magdalena Valley, at coordinates 1°51'14" N latitude and 76°03'05" W longitude (see figure 1)[1]. Positioned at an altitude of 1318 meters above sea level, Pitalito is near the point where the Central and Eastern Andes mountain ranges originate. With a total area of 666 km² [1], the geographical characteristics of the municipality provide a unique setting to explore how access to education can impact both urban and rural development.

This analysis emphasizes the need for local policies to address not only the expansion of educational infrastructure but also the equitable distribution of resources and the provision of easy access for all residents. These elements are essential for effective urban planning and overall social well-being.

Figure 1: Bogota Location. Source: authors.

The municipality of Pitalito currently has a total population of 133,205 inhabitants [6]. Of this population, 51.7% have completed primary education, 23.9% have reached secondary education, 0.47% have technical training, and only 0.58% have attained a university degree. Additionally, 23.3% of the population lacks any formal educational qualifications [19].

In terms of primary and secondary education, there is a notable preference for public education, with 88.43% of students enrolled in public institutions, while 11.57% are attending private schools [2]. Regarding technical and higher education, the municipality supports over 1,700 students enrolled in various institutions, including Uniminuto, Universidad Surcolombiana, Antonio Nariño, the National Training Service (SENA), the Higher School of Public Administration (ESAP), and Universidad Gran Colombiana, among others [2].

Although the educational system in Pitalito largely meets the population's needs, there is a clear need to strengthen institutions to improve access in areas with service gaps. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of educational coverage in Pitalito is proposed, aimed at identifying isolated areas and assessing potential changes in accessibility in the coming years.

Territorial accessibility emerges as a critical tool in this research, underscoring the need for a thorough review of existing literature to build a robust conceptual framework. The concept of "Accessibility" in this study is primarily based on Hansen's 1959 definition, which frames it as the potential for interaction opportunities [11]. However, the concept has evolved with various interpretations since the early 20th century [3], although some key enriching elements have been lost in certain cases [21]. In this research, accessibility is understood as the ease with which citizens can engage in

various activities using different modes of transportation [15], thereby promoting economic development and growth [17].

Numerous studies have explored the link between accessibility and education, contributing valuable insights to our case study [7, 20, 24, 13]. Moreover, there are multiple applications of this concept in other scientific fields that further enrich the analysis [4, 5, 10, 16, 12, 14, 22, 23].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The mechanics of evaluation is based on the execution of 5 fundamental processes, each of these with its respective subroutines, which guarantee an adequate execution of the research.

Information Collection

By employing advanced data mining techniques, a comprehensive analysis of the available databases is initiated, covering both municipal administration data and information from various external entities. This approach not only aids in identifying but also in consolidating the critical digital resources necessary for conducting the research effectively. Within this framework, a set of key variables is developed to be considered throughout the study, which includes a detailed digital database of educational institutions, along with the core infrastructure network of the Pitalito municipality. Furthermore, the existing database is refined and expanded to ensure that all relevant information is up-to-date and easily accessible. This enhancement significantly contributes to conducting a more precise and thorough evaluation within the research, enabling a deeper understanding and more accurate results.

Development, implementation, and refinement of essential digital components.

As part of this methodological approach, various variables are gathered and processed using advanced

digital tools. These variables are subsequently synthesized and organized to create representative models of the different entities involved in the study, aiming to effectively assess territorial accessibility. Key variables include the existing and planned future road infrastructure network of the municipality, precise georeferencing of educational institutions, and the detailed construction of polygons representing various factors relevant to the analysis. Additionally, supplementary spatial and demographic data are integrated to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the local environment. This enriched dataset enables a more thorough and accurate evaluation of accessibility within the municipality of Pitalito, ensuring that all critical aspects are considered for effective planning and development.

Road network

Building upon the characteristic elements gathered during the information collection phase, the road infrastructure network of the municipality is meticulously constructed and refined. Each component of the network is carefully adjusted and enhanced to facilitate the accurate execution of the accessibility evaluation. The network's key elements, including nodes and arcs, are integral in representing the various connections and intersections within the operational software [8] (Figure 2). These nodes and arcs serve as the foundational

framework of the road system, allowing for a detailed mapping of the municipality's transportation grid. Additionally, further enhancements are made to improve the precision and reliability of the network model. This refined infrastructure network becomes a crucial tool in evaluating how effectively the municipality's roadways support accessibility, ensuring that all relevant factors are accounted for in the analysis.

To assess the level of impact on future accessibility, the vehicular infrastructure network is established with the various proposed interventions slated for 2031, as illustrated in Figure 4. It is crucial to emphasize that these interventions will not be executed all at once; rather, they consist of a series of planned actions to be carried out over the years. This phased approach aims to ensure that by the target year, the total execution of the proposed infrastructure improvements will be realized. Each intervention will be strategically implemented at different intervals, allowing for careful monitoring and assessment of their effectiveness as they unfold. This long-term perspective not only enhances the overall quality of the infrastructure but also contributes to improved accessibility and connectivity within the municipality, ultimately benefiting the community as a whole.

Figure 3: Road network. Source: authors.

After constructing the transport networks, the next step is to geographically locate the existing educational facilities within the municipality, as illustrated in Figure 3. Each facility, when evaluated, is referred to as a "facility," a term specifically associated with the ArcMap software, which serves as a foundational element in the evaluation process. This designation is crucial for organizing and analyzing the data within the software, ensuring that each educational institution is accurately represented and integrated into the overall assessment of accessibility and infrastructure.

Accessibility curves

To thoroughly assess the impact of future interventions on the road network, the study correlates accessibility outcomes for each network configuration. This process allows for the determination of the percentage of accessibility savings, which is calculated using Equation 1. Based on the results, an accessibility savings matrix is formulated, which is similar to the approach used for accessibility assessment. Following this, the Geoprocessing Intersect tool is employed to generate representative savings curves. These curves visually depict the efficiency gains from the proposed

network improvements, providing a clear understanding of how the interventions will enhance overall accessibility within the municipality.

$$\% \text{ saving} = \left(\frac{T_v \text{ current} - T_v \text{ future}}{T_v \text{ current}} \right) * 100 \quad (1)$$

Figure 3: Future Road network and facilities. Source: authors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Current scenario

Based on the thorough analysis of the basic road network, Figure 4 was generated, illustrating the variation in travel times to educational institutions, segmented into 0.5-minute intervals. A radial pattern is observed with a pronounced trend towards the central-southern sector of the municipality, where the lowest travel cost is achieved. In contrast, in the peripheral areas, a maximum travel time of 8.5 minutes is noted, indicating that, while there is an increase in travel time, no significant disconnection is present.

Figure 5 shows the behavior resulting from the correlation of variables derived from the intersection of polygons. It is highlighted that, for more than 50% of the points in both variables, a maximum time of just 3 minutes is required, demonstrating optimal accessibility for the basic road network. Additionally, although a parallel trend is observed between the graphs, with a discrepancy of up to 12 points, the similarity in behavior suggests that accessibility is comparable across each variable. This analysis underscores the efficiency of the basic road network in providing adequate access to educational institutions, even in the more distant areas.

Figure 4: Accessibility curves in current Scenario. Source: authors.

Figure 5: Coverage curves in current Scenario. Source: authors.

Future Scenario

As a result of the evaluation of accessibility to educational centers within the future road infrastructure network, Figure 6 illustrates the variation in travel costs across the municipality at 2.5-minute intervals. Similar to the base road network, a radial coverage pattern is observed, with a notable preference for the central area of the municipality. The coverage is particularly high in the representative ranges of 2.5 and 5 minutes, encompassing approximately 40% of the municipality's area. Conversely, a maximum travel cost of 17.5 minutes is identified due to the expansion of road corridors into peripheral sectors. However, the areas with travel times below this maximum do not constitute a significant percentage of the total area.

Additionally, Figure 7 is presented, which displays the coverage percentage generated by each analyzed variable. It is essential to recognize that the population count in this scenario shows a significant increase due to the population expansion reported by DANE. The difference between the curves reported in comparison to the base network indicates a decrease of 5 percentage points, resulting in a separation of up to 7%. For 50% of the considered variables (population and area), the coverage level requires a maximum time of up to 6 minutes. Although this is twice the time recorded in the base network, it remains an adequate level of coverage given the substantial population growth projected by the intervention year.

Figure 6: Accessibility curves in future Scenario. Source: authors.

Figure 7: Coverage curves in future Scenario. Source: authors.

To gain a more detailed view of the impact on accessibility caused by the proposed road interventions towards educational centers, Figure 8 was created. This figure illustrates the savings notifications at 10 percentage point intervals. The comparison between the future road network and the base network reveals savings sectors approaching 35%, with some reaching up to 100%.

However, the majority of the savings fall between 30% and 60%. The remaining 75% does not show significant savings from the implemented interventions; nonetheless, this does not indicate a negative effect, especially when considering the substantial population growth anticipated by the year of study.

Figure 8: Saving gradient. Source: authors.

In Figure 9, the perceived savings percentages are illustrated, showing that the pattern across the curves is consistent. This indicates that the proposed interventions have a uniform effect on both the surface area and the population. Furthermore, it is observed that at least 40% of the variables experience savings of up to 10%. This reduction in travel costs, within the study's

timeframe, signifies a notable enhancement in accessibility. The findings reflect an effective optimization of the roadway interventions, providing equitable benefits across different areas and the population within the municipality. This improved accessibility highlights the successful impact of the planned changes.

Figure 9: Saving coverage. Source: authors.

Conclusions

The assessment of accessibility to schools in the municipality of Pitalito, based on the current situation, demonstrates a highly efficient level of access. Residents are able to reach at least one educational institution within a travel time of less than 8 minutes. In the future scenario, the analysis indicates that accessibility remains at optimal levels, with a significant percentage of both the population and the area still being covered

within the same 8-minute travel time. Despite the increase in population, efficient access to at least one school is maintained throughout the municipality.

It is important to recognize that the study does not account for the specific locations of registered users at each educational institution. Consequently, there is no guarantee that every resident will meet the specified travel times. Nevertheless, the study serves as a robust foundation for allocating school placements to residents living near the educational centers. This provides

a valuable reference for optimizing the distribution of educational resources and enhancing planning efforts for future developments.

Acknowledgements

The authors express their sincere gratitude to the members of the GIMS (Grupo de Investigación en Movilidad Sostenible) and the PIT (Programa de Investigación en Transporte, Movilidad y Territorio) research groups of the Universidad Nacional de Colombia, for their support within the project.

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